

APPROACHES TO TRANSFORM YOUNG LIVES IN CONFLICT SETTINGS: REDEFINING REHABILITATION PROGRAM EFFORTS FOR COMMUNITY HEALING

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the implementation of rehabilitation approaches and community-based programs by Local Government Units (LGUs) in transforming the lives of children in conflict with the law (CICL). It employed a descriptive-correlational quantitative research design to examine how primary, secondary, and tertiary rehabilitation interventions relate to the perceived effectiveness of community-based programs. The study involved 150 respondents, including CICL, their parents or guardians, and LGU personnel across five cities in Metro Manila and Southern Luzon. Using quota sampling and a researcher-developed questionnaire, data were collected and analyzed through weighted mean, standard deviation, and Pearson's correlation. Results showed that LGU rehabilitation approaches were perceived as highly implemented, while community-based programs were viewed as highly effective across all indicators, including life skills development, health services, and family welfare. A strong positive correlation ($r = .836$, $p < .05$) was found between rehabilitation approaches and the effectiveness of community-based programs. These findings affirm that LGUs play a pivotal role in providing integrated, responsive services that promote sustainable rehabilitation and community reintegration for CICL. It is recommended that LGUs enhance inter-agency collaboration and expand access to mental health and family-based support to strengthen tertiary interventions.

Keywords: *Rehabilitation Approaches, Community-Based Programs, Children in Conflict with the Law, LGU Intervention, Sustainable Reintegration*

INTRODUCTION

The plight of children in conflict is a pressing issue both internationally and within the Philippine context wherein they are caught in the crossfire of armed conflicts, often subjected to violence and exploitation. In the Philippines, reports indicate that, driven by socio-economic pressures and the allure of perceived empowerment, many children often serve not only as combatants but also in support roles, reflecting the complexity of the relationship between community and coercion due to their involvement in conflict settings (United Nations, 2024). The international, national, and local communities have acknowledged the urgency of addressing these issues, leading to various initiatives aimed at safeguarding children's rights and promoting their rehabilitation, particularly those coursed through the local government units.

The rights of Filipino children in armed conflict are pressing issues that intersect with both international and national legal frameworks (Morales, 2022). These frameworks reflect various legal instruments and obligations that aim to protect children in conflict with the law. The Philippines has enacted several laws aligned with international standards regarding children's rights such as Republic Act No. 7610, known as the Special Protection of Children Against Abuse, Exploitation, and Discrimination Act, and its amendment Republic Act No. 9231. These laws reinforce protections for vulnerable children and expand the definition of abuse to include psychological, physical, and emotional maltreatment.

The legal framework governing children in conflict with the law (CICL) is primarily established through Republic Act No. 9344 or the Juvenile Justice and Welfare Act of 2006, which emphasizes rehabilitation over punishment. Its amendment, Republic Act No. 10630, strengthens the juvenile system, clarifies procedures for handling CICL, and reinforces the role of local governments in managing intervention centers (Juvenile Justice and Welfare Council, 2024). One of the rehabilitation programs implemented under this law is Bahay Pag-asa, a government-mandated intervention center that provides temporary residential care for CICL aged 15 to 18 awaiting court disposition or undergoing intervention programs.

Despite the presence of these legal safeguards and interventions, challenges persist in the effective implementation of rehabilitation programs at the local level. Community-based programs designed to transform the lives of children in conflict with the law often encounter issues related to funding, staffing, and integration. Furthermore, existing studies lack comprehensive assessments on the actual implementation of rehabilitation approaches and how these relate to the community-based programs of LGUs.

Hence, this study seeks to address this gap by assessing the implementation of rehabilitation approaches and community-based programs of LGUs, and examining their interrelationship in transforming the lives of CICL.

Research Questions

Specifically, it sought to answer the following problems:

1. What is the assessment of the respondents on the rehabilitation approaches implemented by the local government unit to transform the lives of children in conflict with law as to:
 - 1.1 Primary Intervention
 - 1.2 Secondary Intervention
 - 1.3 Tertiary Intervention?
2. What is the assessment of the respondents on the community-based programs of the LGU to transform the lives of children in conflict with law in terms of: Competency and life skills development, Socio-cultural and recreational activities, Community volunteer projects, Leadership training, Social services, Homelife services, Health services, Spiritual enrichment, Community and family welfare services?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the rehabilitation approaches implemented and the community-based programs implemented by the LGU?

METHODOLOGY

This study used a descriptive-correlational quantitative research design to examine the relationship between the rehabilitation approaches implemented by Local Government Units (LGUs) and the effectiveness of their community-based programs for children in conflict with the law (CICL). The descriptive component enabled the assessment of how primary, secondary, and tertiary rehabilitation interventions are implemented, while the correlational aspect allowed the researcher to determine whether a statistically significant relationship exists between rehabilitation efforts and community-based service delivery.

The study involved 150 respondents, composed of 50 CICL, 50 parents or guardians, and 50 LGU officials or personnel. The selected LGUs were from five locations: Mandaluyong, Muntinlupa, Las Piñas, Sta. Rosa Laguna, and Biñan Laguna. A quota sampling technique was employed, ensuring equal representation across the three respondent groups in each LGU.

The participants in this research were drawn from three key groups, selected based on specific eligibility criteria: (1) CICL must have stayed in a rehabilitation center for at least three months and be actively involved in LGU programs; (2) parents or guardians must be legally responsible for the child and have observed or participated in relevant center activities; and (3) LGU personnel must have a direct role in planning, implementing, or monitoring CICL rehabilitation or community-based programs. All respondents were briefed on the study's purpose and voluntarily provided informed consent.

The study was conducted across the five cities in Metro Manila and Southern Luzon based on the presence of operational rehabilitation facilities and active participation in

national mandates under the Juvenile Justice and Welfare Act. These locations were selected due to their accessibility and the presence of structured CICL programs.

Data were collected using a researcher-developed survey questionnaire, constructed in alignment with the study's objectives and guided by Republic Act No. 9344. The instrument was composed of two major sections: (1) the implementation of LGU-led rehabilitation approaches—covering primary, secondary, and tertiary interventions; and (2) the effectiveness of LGU community-based programs—covering areas such as life skills development, health services, leadership training, and community and family welfare. Items were rated using a 5-point Likert scale, measuring both the level of implementation and perceived effectiveness.

To ensure content validity and clarity, the instrument was reviewed by three domain experts: a social work academic, a rehabilitation center director, and a statistician. Their feedback was incorporated into the final version. The instrument was pilot-tested with 25 individuals not included in the final sample, and its internal consistency was verified using Cronbach's Alpha.

Data collection was carried out through a combination of in-person and digital distribution. For centers with limited digital access, printed questionnaires were personally administered. All respondents were provided clear instructions, and every form included a confidentiality statement. Completed responses were checked for completeness, encoded in Microsoft Excel, and imported into SPSS Version 27 for statistical analysis.

The study complied with the highest ethical standards in human subjects research. Participants were fully informed of the study's purpose, procedures, and their right to withdraw at any time. No financial incentives were given. All identifying data were removed to ensure anonymity. The study adhered to both institutional and national ethical guidelines, especially concerning research involving minors and vulnerable populations.

Statistical tools were used to analyze the data. The weighted mean and standard deviation summarized the central tendency and dispersion of responses related to rehabilitation approaches and community-based program effectiveness. Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) was used to determine whether a significant relationship exists between the two variables, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$. Correlation values were interpreted using accepted guidelines: values between 0.60 and 0.79 indicate a strong positive relationship, and values between 0.80 and 1.00 indicate a very strong positive relationship.

RESULTS

Table 1
Assessment of the Respondents on the Rehabilitation Approaches Implemented by the Local Government Unit to Transform the Lives of Children in Conflict with the Law

INDICATORS	CLASSIFICATION	MEAN	SD	INTERPRETATION	RANK
1. Primary Intervention	Child	4.94	0.29	Highly Implemented	1
	Parents-Guardian	4.98	0.14	Highly Implemented	
	LGU Official-Employee	4.93	0.27	Highly Implemented	
	Combined	4.95	0.24	Highly Implemented	
2. Secondary Intervention	Child	4.88	0.32	Highly Implemented	2
	Parents-Guardian	4.98	0.16	Highly Implemented	
	LGU Official-Employee	4.91	0.32	Highly Implemented	
	Combined	4.92	0.28	Highly Implemented	
3. Tertiary Intervention	Child	4.87	0.28	Highly Implemented	3
	Parents-Guardian	4.97	0.21	Highly Implemented	
	LGU Official-Employee	4.87	0.37	Highly Implemented	
	Combined	4.90	0.30	Highly Implemented	
Overall Mean	Child	4.89	0.29	Highly Implemented	
	Parents-Guardian	4.98	0.17	Highly Implemented	
	LGU Official-Employee	4.90	0.31	Highly Implemented	
	Combined	4.92	0.26	Highly Implemented	

LEGEND: HIGHLY IMPLEMENTED (=4.51-5.0); IMPLEMENTED (=3.51-4.50); MODERATELY IMPLEMENTED (=2.51-3.50); SLIGHTLY IMPLEMENTED (=1.51-2.50); NOT IMPLEMENTED AT ALL (=1.0-1.50)

Table 1 denotes the summary on assessment of the respondents on the rehabilitation approaches implemented by the local government unit to transform the lives of children in conflict with the law. Data reveals that all indicators is interpreted as to "highly implemented" with an overall mean of 4.92 and standard deviation of 0.26. The highest-rated intervention is the "Primary Intervention," with a mean of 4.95 and a standard deviation of 0.24, indicating that it is perceived as "Highly Implemented" by all classifications (children, parents-guardians, and LGU employees). This intervention focuses on the initial stage of addressing the children's needs before they engage in serious offenses. On the other hand, the lowest-rated intervention is the "Tertiary Intervention," with a mean of 4.90 and a standard deviation of 0.30, which, though still "Highly Implemented," reflects a slightly lower perception of effectiveness in the more intensive rehabilitation efforts aimed at children who have already committed serious offenses.

Table 2 displays the summary on the assessment of the respondents on the effectiveness of the community-based programs of the LGU to transform the lives of the children in conflict with the law. It is observed that all indicators are interpreted as to "highly effective" with a composite mean of 4.93 and standard deviation of 0.28. The highest-ranked indicator is "Community and Family Welfare Services," with a combined

mean of 4.95 and a standard deviation of 0.22, reflecting its significance in addressing the needs of children in conflict with the law and their families.

Table 2
Assessment of the Respondents on the Effectiveness of the Community-Based Programs of the LGU to Transform the Lives of Children in Conflict with the Law

INDICATORS	CLASSIFICATION	MEAN	SD	INTERPRETATION	RANK
1. Competency and Life Skills Development	Child	4.88	0.39	Highly Effective	6.5
	Parents-Guardian	4.98	0.18	Highly Effective	
	LGU Official-Employee	4.90	0.28	Highly Effective	
	Combined	4.92	0.30	Highly Effective	
2. Socio-Cultural and Recreational Activities	Child	4.88	0.39	Highly Effective	4.5
	Parents-Guardian	4.97	0.21	Highly Effective	
	LGU Official-Employee	4.90	0.28	Highly Effective	
	Combined	4.93	0.28	Highly Effective	
3. Community Volunteer Projects	Child	4.87	0.54	Highly Effective	8.5
	Parents-Guardian	4.97	0.25	Highly Effective	
	LGU Official-Employee	4.90	0.24	Highly Effective	
	Combined	4.91	0.37	Highly Effective	
4. Leadership Training	Child	4.88	0.50	Highly Effective	4.5
	Parents-Guardian	4.98	0.16	Highly Effective	
	LGU Official-Employee	4.92	0.25	Highly Effective	
	Combined	4.93	0.34	Highly Effective	
5. Social Services	Child	4.86	0.52	Highly Effective	6.5
	Parents-Guardian	4.98	0.14	Highly Effective	
	LGU Official-Employee	4.91	0.25	Highly Effective	
	Combined	4.92	0.35	Highly Effective	
6. Homelife Services	Child	4.86	0.51	Highly Effective	8.5
	Parents-Guardian	4.96	0.19	Highly Effective	
	LGU Official-Employee	4.92	0.23	Highly Effective	
	Combined	4.91	0.34	Highly Effective	
7. Health Services	Child	4.90	0.35	Highly Effective	2.5
	Parents-Guardian	4.98	0.14	Highly Effective	
	LGU Official-Employee	4.94	0.21	Highly Effective	
	Combined	4.94	0.25	Highly Effective	
8. Spiritual Enrichment	Child	4.92	0.32	Highly Effective	2.5
	Parents-Guardian	4.99	0.09	Highly Effective	
	LGU Official-Employee	4.92	0.24	Highly Effective	
	Combined	4.94	0.24	Highly Effective	
9. Community and Family Welfare Services	Child	4.93	0.29	Highly Effective	1
	Parents-Guardian	4.98	0.14	Highly Effective	
	LGU Official-Employee	4.94	0.21	Highly Effective	
	Combined	4.95	0.22	Highly Effective	
Overall Mean	Child	4.89	0.40	Highly Effective	
	Parents-Guardian	4.98	0.16	Highly Effective	
	LGU Official-Employee	4.92	0.21	Highly Effective	
	Combined	4.93	0.28	Highly Effective	

LEGEND: VERY EFFECTIVE (=4.51-5.0); EFFECTIVE (=3.51-4.50); MODERATELY EFFECTIVE (=2.51-3.50); SLIGHTLY EFFECTIVE (=1.51-2.50); NOT EFFECTIVE AT ALL (=1.0-1.50)

All classifications—children, parents/guardians, and LGU officials—rated this as highly effective, with parents/guardians scoring it the highest at 4.98 with a standard deviation of 0.14. Conversely, the lowest-ranked indicators are "Community Volunteer Projects" and "Homelife Services," both tied with a combined mean of 4.91 and a standard deviation of 0.37 and 0.34, respectively. While these are still considered highly effective, the slightly lower ratings imply opportunities for improvement in volunteer-driven and home-based support mechanisms. The classification data show that children scored these lowest indicators at 4.87 with standard deviations of 0.54 and 0.51, indicating variability in their experiences with these services.

Table 3
Significant Relationship between the Rehabilitation Approaches Implemented and the Community-Based Programs Implemented by the LGU

Variable Tested		R-Value	Degree of Correlation	Sig Value (2 tailed)	Decision on HO	Interpretation
Rehabilitation Approaches Implemented	Community-Based Programs Implemented by the LGU	.836	Very Strong Positive Correlation	.000	Reject	Significant

Table 3 presents the significant relationship between the rehabilitation approaches implemented and the community-based programs implemented by the LGU. The findings revealed a significant relationship between the Rehabilitation Approaches Implemented and the Community-Based Programs Implemented by the LGU, as indicated by an R-value of 0.836, which denotes a strong positive correlation. The significance value (Sig. = 0.000) is below the 0.05 threshold, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis and affirming the statistical significance of this relationship. This result highlights that the rehabilitation strategies employed by the LGU are closely and positively associated with the effectiveness and comprehensiveness of the community-based programs they implement. It implies that the success of one variable reinforces and complements the other, underscoring a synergistic effect between these initiatives.

DISCUSSION

As shown in Table 1, the rehabilitation programs implemented by the local government are viewed as highly implemented due to their holistic approach in addressing the varying needs of children in conflict with the law at different stages. Primary interventions focus on preventing delinquent behavior through education, social support, and guidance, offering children at risk opportunities to redirect their lives. Secondary interventions target children exhibiting early signs of delinquency, aiming to prevent escalation into more serious offenses, while tertiary interventions provide intensive rehabilitation, reformation, and reintegration support for children who have committed serious offenses. The high ratings reflect the respondents' recognition of the comprehensive nature of these programs and their effectiveness in transforming lives. Literature supports the effectiveness of such multi-tiered interventions in reducing recidivism and fostering successful reintegration into society (Ganie et al., 2022; Wahyudi et al., 2022; Kilkelly & Pleysier, 2023). Despite slight variations in ratings for tertiary programs, which require significant resources and intersectoral coordination, the overall success of the programs in providing mentorship, educational sponsorship, and mental health services underscores their applicability and necessity (Biset, 2023). These interventions equip children with the tools to overcome past offenses and lead productive lives, ensuring a long-term impact on community safety and individual transformation (Rawanda, 2021). To sustain and enhance the effectiveness of these programs, LGUs should prioritize resource allocation and strengthen interagency collaboration, particularly for tertiary interventions that require intensive support. Expanding access to mental health services, mentorship opportunities, and legal assistance will ensure that the holistic approach remains impactful across all intervention levels (Løken & Hauken, 2021). Regular evaluations and feedback mechanisms should be implemented to adapt the programs to the evolving needs of children, further reinforcing their positive impact on reducing recidivism and promoting societal reintegration (Wahyudi et al., 2022).

In Table 2, the data reveals the high effectiveness of community-based programs implemented by the LGU can be attributed to their comprehensive interventions that address multiple facets of rehabilitation and skill-building. Programs such as health services, spiritual enrichment, and leadership training foster physical, emotional, and social well-being, while socio-cultural activities and life skills development promote reintegration into the community (Bowers, 2023; Bates et al., 2020). Parents and guardians rated these programs the highest, reflecting their direct observation of improvements in their children's behavior and opportunities, while children, though rating the programs slightly lower, still expressed positive perceptions, indicating that the services met their needs to a significant degree (Ganie et al., 2022; Gonzales et al., 2023). These findings align with studies that emphasize structured, holistic interventions foster personal development and positive outcomes for at-risk youth (Hadiana et al., 2021). The community-based programs are highly applicable and effective in transforming the lives of children in conflict with the law, as they address multifaceted needs and create a supportive environment conducive to personal and social growth (Zulinto et al., 2021). The strong alignment of community and institutional efforts reinforces their applicability. By continuously refining and expanding services like volunteer projects and homelife

support, LGUs can further enhance the transformative potential of these programs, ensuring sustainable and inclusive development for children in conflict with the law. To maximize the impact of community-based programs, LGUs should focus on continuously refining and expanding services to address evolving needs, ensuring that these programs remain comprehensive and holistic. By strengthening areas such as volunteer projects and homelife support, these initiatives can further empower children in conflict with the law, leading to long-term, sustainable rehabilitation and reintegration (Agaskar et al., 2020; Geiger & Okpych, 2021). Additionally, LGUs should consider the varying perceptions of different stakeholders to fine-tune the programs and enhance their effectiveness for both children and families (Ganie et al., 2022).

It is observed in Table 3 that there was strong positive correlation between the Rehabilitation Approaches Implemented and the Community-Based Programs Implemented by the LGU, as indicated by an R-value of 0.836. The strong correlation can be attributed to the holistic design and execution of LGU community-based programs, which integrate rehabilitation approaches into their frameworks. Rehabilitation strategies often encompass diverse interventions, such as skill development, health services, socio-cultural activities, and family welfare services, all of which are key components of community-based programs (Cale, 2024). This interconnectedness ensures that programs are not only rehabilitative but also restorative, aiming to rebuild the lives of children in conflict with the law by addressing the root causes of their challenges and facilitating their reintegration into society (Stover et al., 2024; Wahyudi et al., 2022). Furthermore, the LGU's focus on evidence-based practices and community involvement ensures that the programs remain relevant, sustainable, and impactful (Gonzales et al., 2023). Thus, a well-executed rehabilitation plan that integrates skill-building and social reintegration activities can foster resilience and self-reliance among children in conflict with the law. Likewise, community-based programs that incorporate strong rehabilitation elements are better equipped to address individual and collective needs, creating a supportive environment for long-term change (King et al., 2021). According to Stover et al. (2024), effective interventions must consider multiple layers of influence, from individual to community-level factors, to achieve meaningful outcomes. The significant relationship between rehabilitation approaches and LGU community-based programs highlights the importance of strategic alignment and integration in addressing the needs of children in conflict with the law. This relationship ensures that programs are not only comprehensive but also adaptive to the unique challenges faced by this vulnerable group (Copeland et al., 2022; Aazami, 2023). By leveraging this synergy, LGUs can deliver impactful and sustainable solutions, promoting holistic rehabilitation and fostering community resilience.

These findings affirm the importance of a holistic and coordinated approach to rehabilitation and reintegration. With strong alignment between LGU-led interventions and community-based programs, the study highlights the power of integrated efforts in shaping positive outcomes for CICL.

Conclusions

1. Respondents perceive the local government's rehabilitation approaches as highly implemented across primary, secondary, and tertiary interventions. This indicates that the LGU has effectively established a comprehensive rehabilitation framework. However, regular evaluation and continuous improvement are needed to ensure these interventions remain responsive to the evolving needs of children in conflict with the law.
2. Respondents rate the community-based programs of the LGU as highly effective in competency and life skills development, socio-cultural and recreational activities, community volunteer projects, leadership training, social services, homelife services, health services, spiritual enrichment, and community and family welfare services. This demonstrates that the LGU's community-based programs are addressing a wide range of developmental and social needs for children in conflict with the law.
3. A significant relationship exists between the rehabilitation approaches implemented and the community-based programs of the LGU. This consensus is a positive indicator that the rehabilitation efforts are perceived consistently across all stakeholders, which can foster collaboration and trust in the program.

Recommendations

1. Conduct regular evaluations of the LGU's rehabilitation framework through quarterly reviews and stakeholder consultations to identify gaps and emerging needs. Form a multidisciplinary committee, including LGU employees, psychologists, and community leaders, to oversee these evaluations. Utilize findings to adjust interventions and maintain responsiveness to children's evolving challenges.
2. Expand the community-based programs by incorporating more targeted initiatives, such as mental health support and career readiness training. Collaborate with local schools, religious organizations, and volunteer groups to enhance the scope and reach of these programs. Assign program coordinators to ensure efficient implementation and track effectiveness.
3. Strengthen the integration between rehabilitation approaches and community-based programs by developing a unified implementation plan. Create an interdepartmental task force within the LGU to synchronize efforts and share resources between rehabilitation teams and community program facilitators. Schedule quarterly workshops to refine strategies and track progress.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study confirmed that informed consent was obtained from the subsequent respondents. The participants had the liberty to withdraw from the study at any moment, their anonymity was preserved, their well-being was protected, no conflicts of interest

were present in the study's execution, plagiarism was rigorously avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the results, and the findings were utilized solely for research purposes.

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